

Craters at Qasr Shemamok (Kurdistan, Iraq)

OPPORTUNITIES AND PROBLEMS FOR EXCAVATIONS

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Résumé : Des cratères à Qasr Shemamok (Kurdistan, Irak)

Qasr Shemamok – une cité antique, identifiée, au moins pendant la période assyrienne, par le toponyme de *Kilizu* – a été l'un des centres régionaux du « pays d'Assur » dès la fin de l'âge du Bronze et pendant l'âge du Fer. Son acropole se distingue par la présence de vastes cratères, bien visibles sur son sommet. Remplis progressivement par la colluvion et par des remblais, ces cratères ont été produits au cours d'opérations de guerre récentes (2002-2003) : les bombardements effectués par la coalition menée par les États-Unis étaient destinés à la destruction d'une base militaire irakienne, installée en bonne position stratégique pour contrôler les routes traversant la plaine du Shiwazor, de la rive du Zab Supérieur jusqu'à la cité d'Erbil. Si les bombes ont détruit l'occupation militaire visée, elles ont également endommagé une partie des niveaux archéologiques ; cependant, les cratères nous ont également offert l'opportunité d'atteindre rapidement les vestiges des périodes plus anciennes. En effet, les premiers sondages avaient montré que les occupations de l'âge du Fer étaient couvertes par environ 5 mètres de couches datables aux époques post-assyriennes. Ainsi, la fouille d'un cratère situé sur le côté nord-est de l'acropole aurait pu nous donner assez rapidement une idée plus précise de la séquence stratigraphique de cette zone. La première partie de cet article présente les phases d'avancement et les premiers résultats de cette opération, illustrant à la fois les progrès et les difficultés rencontrées. La deuxième partie montre les caractères taphonomiques d'une « bombturbation » dans une stratigraphie archéologique.

Mots-clés : Qasr Shemamok, Kurdistan, fouilles, stratigraphie, occupation militaire, « bombturbation », cratère, explosion.

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Abstract : Qasr Shemamok – an ancient city identified by the toponym of *Kilizu* at least during the Assyrian period – was one of the regional centres of “The Land of Assur”, since the end of the Bronze Age and during the Iron Age. Its acropolis features nowadays a series of craters of considerable size, clearly visible on the top of the site. These craters, filled up with colluvium layers and intentional backfills, have been produced by some bombings by US-led coalition during the recent wars (2002-2003). The attack targeted an Iraqi military facility placed on the acropolis, meant to take advantage of its location as a strategic road checkpoint in the Shiwazor valley, between the Upper Zab valley and the city of Erbil. Coalition’s explosive ordnances destroyed not only the military base, but also a part of the archaeological levels that laid underneath. Nevertheless, eventually they offered us an opportunity to reach quicker the remains of the ancient settlements. Soundings on the citadel have shown that Iron Age levels were sealed by about 5 meters of Post-Assyrian layers. Under such circumstances, we chose to focus a part of our work on a crater located on the north-eastern side of the citadel, in order to gain a more precise understanding of the stratigraphic sequence in this area. In the first part of this article, we present the different phases of development and the first results of this operation, discussing both progress and difficulties. The second part of this study explains the taphonomic properties of a “bombturbation” in an archaeological stratigraphy.

Keywords : Qasr Shemamok, Kurdistan, excavation, stratigraphy, military occupation, “bombturbation”, crater, explosion.

ملخص / پوخته / خلاصه

الحفر في قصر شماموك (كردستان، العراق): الفرص ومشاكل الحفريات

قصر شماموك - مدينة قديمة - تم تحديدها على الأقل خلال الفترة الآشورية وفق اسم كيليزو، والتي كانت واحدة من المراكز الإقليمية لـ "بلاد آشور" في نهاية العصر البرونزي وخلال العصر الحديدي. يتميز أكرابولها (قمة التل) بوجود فوهات كبيرة، يمكن رؤيتها بوضوح في قمة التل. وتمتلك هذه الفوهات بشكل مستمر بالردميات والحجارة. تم إنتاج هذه الحفر خلال العمليات الحربية الأخيرة (2002-2003) نتيجة عمليات القصف التي كانت تقوم به قوات التحالف الذي تقوده الولايات المتحدة والتي كانت تهدف إلى تدمير قاعدة عسكرية عراقية ذات الموقع الاستراتيجي والتي كانت تسيطر على الطرق التي تعبر سهل شهرزور من ضفة نهر الزاب الأعلى إلى مدينة أربيل. وحينما دمرت القنابل القاعدة العسكرية المستهدفة، فإنها ألحقت أضراراً ببعض السويات الأثرية في الموقع. ومع ذلك، فإن الحفر قد أتاحت لنا الفرصة للوصول بسرعة إلى سويات العصور القديمة. وأظهرت الاستطلاعات الأولى في الموقع أن طبقات العصر الحديدي كانت مغطاة بحوالي 5 أمتار من السويات المؤرخة بفترات ما بعد الفترة الآشورية. وبذلك فقد مكن التنقيب في حفرة على الجانب الشمالي الشرقي من الأكرابول من أن يعطينا فكرة سريعة عن التسلسل الطبقي لهذه المنطقة. يعرض الجزء الأول من هذه المقالة مراحل التقدم والنتائج الأولى لهذه العملية، موضحاً التقدم المحرز والصعوبات المصادفة. ويعرض الجزء الثاني الدور المزيج للتفجير في الطبقات الأثرية.

الكلمات المفتاحية: قصر شماموك، كردستان، الحفريات، الطباقية، الإشغال العسكري، "تفجير القنابل"، الحفرة، الانفجار.

چاله هه‌لکه‌نراوه‌کانی گردی قه‌سر شه‌مامۆک (کوردستان، عێراق): شانص و هه‌لکۆلین

پوخت: گردی قه‌سر شه‌مامۆک-شارێکی کۆن، ناسراوه، له‌ سه‌رده‌می ئاشوریه‌کاندا، وه‌ له‌ ناوی جوگرافیی ئاشوریه‌کاندا به‌ کێلزو ناسراوه- سه‌ته‌ریکی هه‌ریمايه‌تی ((وولاتی ئاشور بووه)) له‌ کۆتای سه‌رده‌می برونزی و سه‌رده‌می ئاسنی. شوینیکه‌ پره‌ له‌ چالی سه‌ربازی و به‌رگری، که‌وا له‌ ماوه‌ی جه‌نگی کۆتای (2002-2003) دا لیدراوه: وه‌ك برودمانی هاوپه‌یمانان به‌ سه‌رکردایه‌تی ویلايه‌ته‌ یه‌کگرتووکان به‌ مه‌به‌ستی بۆردمانی بکه‌ی سه‌ربازی عێراق، که‌وا شوینیکه‌ گرنگ بووه‌ بۆ زالبون به‌ سه‌ر ئه‌و رینگایانه‌ی که‌وا به‌ ده‌شتی شیوازور تپه‌ر ده‌بن له‌ که‌نار زینی گه‌وره‌و ب‌ وشاری هه‌ولێر. له‌وانیه‌ ئه‌و بۆمبانه‌ بکه‌ سه‌ربازیه‌کانی کردیته‌ ئامانج، به‌لام له‌ هه‌مان کاتدا زیانی به‌ هه‌ندی چینه‌ شوینه‌واریه‌کان گه‌یاندوووه، له‌ گه‌ل ئه‌وه‌شدا، ئه‌م چالانه‌ بوون به‌ ده‌رفه‌تیک بۆ گه‌یشتن به‌ شیویه‌کی خیرا به‌ چینه‌ کۆنه‌کاندا. له‌ راستدا، له‌ ئه‌نجامی هه‌لکۆلینه‌ سه‌ره‌تایه‌کاندا چینی نیشه‌جیوونی سه‌رده‌می ئاسنی له‌ ژیر رووینشی 5 مه‌تر ده‌رکه‌وتوون که‌وا ده‌گه‌رینه‌وه‌ بۆ سه‌رده‌مه‌کانی پیش ئاشوری، وه‌ هه‌روه‌ها، لیدانی چالیک له‌ که‌ناری رۆژه‌ه‌لاقی لوتکه‌ی سه‌ره‌وه‌ بیره‌که‌کی خیرامان ده‌دا به‌ده‌سته‌وه‌ له‌ سه‌ر چینه‌ شوینه‌واریه‌کانی گرده‌که‌. به‌شی یه‌که‌می ئه‌م توێژینه‌وه‌یه‌ قوناغه‌کانی پیکه‌وتن و ئه‌نجامه‌ سه‌ره‌تایه‌کانی ئه‌م پۆپارسۆنه‌ نیشان ده‌دا، که‌وا پێشکه‌وتن و ته‌گه‌ره‌کان نیشان ده‌دا. دووه‌م به‌ش باس له‌ تایه‌مه‌ندی ئه‌و بۆمبارانه‌ ده‌کات که‌وا زانیانیان به‌ چینه‌ شوینه‌واریه‌کان دازو.

ووشه‌ی تپه‌ر: قه‌سر شه‌مامۆک، کوردستان، هه‌لکۆلین، چینه‌ شوینه‌واریه‌کان، نیشه‌گه‌ی سه‌ربازی، بۆمبارکردن، چال، ته‌قاندنه‌وه‌.

حفره‌ها در قصر شیماموک (کردستان، عراق): فرصت‌ها و چالش‌های کاوش‌های باستان‌شناسی

قصر شیماموک، شه‌ری قدیمی ایست که، کم از کم در دوره آشوری مشخص شده و با نام کیلزو یاد میشد؛ این شهر از اواخر عصر مفرغ و در جریان عصر آهن یکی از مراکز محلی «کشور آشور» به‌ شمار میرفت. در بلندای دژ، حفره‌های بزرگی موجود است، که بتدریج توسط کوه‌رفت‌ها و زیاله‌ها پُر شده‌ اند. این حفره‌ها در جریان عملیات نظامی اخیر بین سالهای ۲۰۰۲ و ۲۰۰۳ میلادی ایجاد گردیده‌اند، بمباردمان این ساحه، که توسط قوای ائتلاف به رهبری ایالات متحده صورت گرفت، برای نابودی یک پایگاه نظامی عراقی بود. این پایگاه واقع در نقطه استراتژیک ایست، که راه‌های عبور و مرور از جلگه شیوازور، کرانه علیا زاب تا شهر اربیل را در کنترل دارد. اگرچه این بمب‌ها منجر به تخریب ساحه نظامی گردیدند، آنها قسمتی از لایه‌های باستانی را همچنان ویران کردند؛ در ضمن این حفره‌ها سبب شدند، تا زودتر به بقایای باستانی دوره‌های قدیم دسترسی پیدا نمایم. در واقع ساندازه‌های ابتدایی گواه آنست، که زیستگاه عصر آهن تقریباً توسط ۵ متر لایه باستانی پوشیده شده و قدامت آنها به دوره بعد آشوری بر میگردد. همچنان کاوش یکی از این حفره‌ها، که در گوشه شمال-شرقی دژ واقع شده، میتواند برای ما بطور سرسری، تصور کلی دقیق از توالی لایه‌های این بخش را ارائه کند. قسمت اول این مقاله، مراحل پیشرفت و نتایج اولیه این عملیات کاوش را شرح میدهد، که همزمان بیانگر پیشرفت و مشکلات پیش آمده است. قسمت دوم مشخصات تافونومیکی یا فرایند حفظ شدگی یک «بمب توربسیان 1» را در یک لایه باستانی نشان میدهد. واژه‌های کلیدی: قصر شیماموک، کردستان، کاوش‌ها، چینه/لایه شناسی، اشغال نظامی، «بمب توربسیان» حفره، انفجار.

1. THE TELL OF QASR SHEMAMOK: A STRATEGIC CENTRE FOR THE “LAND OF ASSUR” AND BEYOND (ILARIA CALINI AND MARIA GRAZIA MASETTI-ROUAULT)

1.1. Location of the site and first identifications

The site of Qasr Shemamok covers around 70 hectares⁴ and it is located at about 25 km from Erbil, and about the same distance from the Neo-Assyrian capital of Kalhu/Nimrud and the Tigris River beyond it (Figure 1).

Since the beginning of archaeological research in northern Mesopotamia, the site has been identified as the ancient city called *Kakzu* – a toponym read today, more correctly, as *Kilizu* – thanks to the discovery of cuneiform inscriptions on baked bricks celebrating the construction of a system of urban walls by the Assyrian

king Sennacherib, at the very end of the 8th century B.C.⁵. The excavations of the French team, directed by Olivier Rouault and later by M. G. Masetti-Rouault (Mission Archéologique Française à Qasr Shemamok, MAFQS), ongoing since 2011, have confirmed this identification and the integration of the town into the Assyrian system since the Late Bronze Age⁶.

The discoveries of Sennacherib's ramp, in the southern slope of the “citadel”, and of the remains of Adad-nirari I's palace in the northern one support this claim. However, further study has shown that the occupational

Figure 1: Location of Qasr Shemamok in north-eastern Mesopotamia (©Google Earth, DigitalGlobe, CNES Spot images, MAFQS).

4. The actual surface of the lower town corresponds to the area covered by city walls of Sennacherib's era, but the results of different surveys around the site suggest that, at certain times, the settlement could have been more extensive, up to 100 hectares.

5. LAYARD 1853, p. vi and p. 223-224. See also POSTGATE 1980, p. 591; ROUAULT & MASETTI-ROUAULT 2014, 2015; MASETTI-ROUAULT & ROUAULT 2012; ROUAULT 2015; ROUAULT & MASETTI-ROUAULT 2016; ROUAULT *et al.* 2018a,b.

6. ROUAULT *et al.* 2018a,b.

Figure 2: Map of the Erbil Plain with the Viewshed from Qasr Shemamok. (ArcMap, SRTM, USGS, realised by J.-J. Herr).

Figure 3: U2 aerial imagery of Qasr Shemamok and the surrounding area in 1960 (courtesy of J. Ur).

history of the site is in fact far longer, starting possibly as early as the Chalcolithic period, and continuing until the late Ottoman period.

Thanks to the fertility of its rural landscape and to its position – at the crossroads between the Assyrian capital cities on the Tigris and the region of Erbil/Arbela, and on the way towards the Zagros and northern Iran, as well as to Babylonian territories in the south-east – the site has had a great strategic importance during all historical periods. The viewshed analysis of ArcGIS software determines the raster area visible from the top of the tell (in purple in Figure 2) and shows that Qasr Shemamok, overlooking the entire plain, offers a clear line of sight, over a long distance, to the south-western slope of the Demirdagh and the north-eastern slope of the long anticline hill of the Zurqah Ziraw Dagh (northern part) and Avanah Dagh (southern part). This strategic feature ensured the continuity of its urban structure, though making it the object of

frequent destructions, followed up by heavy reconstruction programs, often determined by the military and logistic needs of the states and empires ruling the region. Located on the left bank of the Shiwazor river – coming from Erbil and entering the Upper Zab just before its confluence into the Tigris –, Qasr Shemamok is formed by a “citadel” and a “lower town”. The latter is now covered by irrigated fields and, in its southern part, by the new Kurdish village of Sa’adawa, rebuilt after a destruction during the last conflicts. This is the reason why we have not yet been able to excavate the lower town, and had to limit our research there to pedestrian and magnetic surveys. Therefore, our excavations have been carried out mainly in the citadel area.

The descriptions given by Henry Layard and Victor Place⁷ after their visits and first trenches at Qasr Shemamok insist on the imposing dimensions of the site. Layard also mentioned the presence, at the top, of ruins of

Figure 4: Satellite Imagery of citadel of Qasr Shemamok with the six large craters marking the surface. (ArcMap, Bing Map, DigitalGlobe, modified by J.-J. Herr).

7. PLACE 1852, p. 463-464.

Figure 5: Aerial view of Qasr Shemamok: the craters and the military installations, 2012 (© MAFQS).

Figure 6: Aerial view of Area B, at the north-eastern corner of the acropolis, 2012 (© MAFQS).

an Ottoman fortress, reused by an Arabic clan for its settlement. Despite these early identifications, no images nor graphic representations of Qasr Shemamok exist until the pictures taken by Doro Levi, the architect of the Italian archaeological team led by Giuseppe Furlani at the beginning of 1933⁸. These pictures – damaged by the flooding of the Arno River in the Florence archaeological museum archives in 1964 – show, among many other views and archaeological contexts and objects, the eastern part of the citadel – where area B is now located – and its centre, where the Italian camp was settled, as marked by the presence of ruins⁹.

At the beginning of the 60's, when the first U2¹⁰ and CORONA¹¹ pictures were taken, the situation had already dramatically changed (Figure 3). The acropolis's surface, almost 30 meters above the Shiwazor river, had been levelled by the Iraqi army, and it was – and still is – marked by a military trench all along its perimeter. Other remains of the Iraqi military installations, such as various sized pits, and the edges of a big platform, are still visible (Figures 4 and 5). When the MAFQS started working on the site in Spring 2011, the situation was, yet again, quite different. The surface of the tell was indeed completely flat as a result of a « 2002 or 2003 American bombing », according to the information provided by the inhabitants of the nearby villages of Sa'adawa and Tarjan and as testified by the presence of craters of different dimensions, now partially filled up by layers of colluvium. Later on, the remains of the Iraqi military installations have been levelled out by mechanical means and the rubble thrown downhill, probably as a local initiative in order to erase every memory of the military occupation.

After a mine clearance operation carried out by a specialised Kurdish military unit, we started our first season of excavation by opening a trench on the southern slope of the tell - called area A -, which goes from the top of

the acropolis to the lower town. Trench A allowed us to make a first stratigraphic assessment of the site, documenting not only the Assyrian occupation, but also important settlements of the Hellenistic, Parthian and Sasanian periods. We can now tentatively propose that Qasr Shemamok could have lost its urban and residential setting since the Early Islamic period, although the citadel continued to be used as a military and administrative centre until the modern times. The first excavation carried out on the acropolis showed that the construction of the Iraqi military base had been set on a flat surface, resulting from the total erasure of the ancient Ottoman period structures still visible to Layard.

1.2. The MAFQS: excavation strategy and first observations

In Spring 2012, we decided to start working on the surface of the acropolis by opening area B at its north-eastern corner (Figure 6). Toward the North, we added to it a sounding dug on the edge of one of the craters (Figure 4, n° 1) created by the bombing. The choice of this specific location for Area B depended on the contextual necessity to create an alignment with the previous excavated Area A, in order to enable us to eventually link the archaeological levels of these two areas. That operation brought us to experience in a concrete way the correlation between the traces of the most ancient and the most recent past. By dealing with this kind of “polemo-shape” craters as part of the archaeological heritage¹², we eventually documented and described not only the remains of ancient occupations, but also the disruptive effects of the recent conflicts on the site.

Being fully aware we had to face significant stratigraphic perturbations due to the explosion, we hoped in this way to reach more quickly the Iron II-III levels we were interested in, exploiting the deep pit created in more

8. FURLANI 1933, 1934c,b,d,a, 1935a,b.

9. ANASTASIO *et al.* 2012, p. 15, Fig. 5; p. 46, Fig. 42.

10. Aerial surveillance program in the Middle East by the U.S. (1958-1960). <https://scholar.harvard.edu/jasonur/u2-aerial-photography-middle-east>.

11. Spy Satellite program. <https://scholar.harvard.edu/jasonur/pages/corona-photography-1>.

12. On the specific issue of the ethical implications of excavating the remains of contemporary history, see POLLOCK 2016.

Figure 7: The bottom of Crater 1 and its eastern profile (© MAFQS, photo by M. G. Masetti-Rouault).

Figure 8: Eastern Section of Chantier B (© MAFQS, photo by J.-J. Herr).

than 4 meters of Sasanian, Parthian and Hellenistic levels of occupation.

Following this risky strategy, we have been progressing quite quickly in our excavations in the north-eastern slope of the citadel. After two seasons of excavation, we have been able to see the entire profile of Crater 1, showing the archaeological remains of walls, floors and ancient deposits in yellow, orange and brown (Figures 7 and 8).

Several fractures appear, due to the blast radius of an air dropped bomb: structures have been disintegrated on 1 meter deep and the stratigraphy has been cut obliquely. This sounding operation allowed us to reach the bottom of the crater and the Post-Assyrian and Neo-Assyrian levels, traversing the Hellenistic, Parthian and Sasanian stratigraphy. The remaining backed bricks visible at the bottom of the crater mark the level 8, dated to the Neo-Assyrian period (Figures 7 and 8). Another sounding, realised during 2017 campaign of excavation in order to explore the Early Neo-Assyrian and the Middle-Assyrian levels, was partially located in the western part of Crater 1, close to the impact point of the bomb, thus showing once again a series of disintegrated and completely burnt layers. However, it should be noted that there was no clear continuity of the burning traces starting from the impact point – where we found, in the previous years, larger parts of the bomb's debris. These layers are separated from the center of the explosion, thus indicating the trajectory of some metallic fragments which have penetrated into the archaeological strata, now marked by the presence of ashes and by chromatic effects of various shades (Figure 9).

Finally, the structures identified immediately west of the crater and belonging to the Parthian level show the effects of the seismic waves of the explosion too, particularly powerful toward the upper part of the crater. In contrast, some segments of a Neo- or Post-Assyrian canalization built in baked bricks, while being very close to the sector perturbed by the fragments of the bomb, did not show any mark of destruction connected with them.

Figure 9: Northern part of area B. Sounding underneath the centre and the western part of Crater 1 with bomb's debris, 2017 (© MAFQS, photo by M. G. Masetti-Rouault).

2. QASR SHEMAMOK, AN “OBSERVATION POINT” FOR THE IRAQI ARMY BEFORE 2003 WAR (JEAN-JACQUES HERR)

2.1. The context of the bombing: identifying the origins of the craters

As seen with the visibility analysis (Figure 2), the high mound of Qasr Shemamok provides an advantageous observation point for the surrounding plain, the Demirdagh and the Zurqah Ziraw Dagh hills, North and East of the *Green Line*. This site and the nearby site of Awena, located 8.5 km to the South West, mark the north-eastern border of the Gwer sub-district of Makhmur district. The eastern border of the Makhmur district corresponds to the former *Green Line*¹³. After the Gulf War, in late 1991, the Iraqi Army moved south of this limit and established military fortified positions along the southern limit of the line. The peripheral trench featuring regular firing positions marked by rectangular or round shape pits as well as nine rectangular pits of 4 m by around 10 m used as defensive firing and observation points by T54/55 Iraqi MBTs (Main Battle Tanks)¹⁴ testify the nature of occupation of the site (Figures 4 to 6 and 10)¹⁵. The pattern of the visibility area combined to placement of the tank's entrenchment pits reveal an eastern and north-eastern focus of the Iraqi army, namely East and North of the *Green Line*. Thus, the tracing of the *Green Line* is correlated to the location of strategic sites such as Qasr Shemamok. The northern part of this boundary corresponds to the southern slope of the Demirdagh, visible from Qasr Shemamok. The high mound of the archaeological site may have been a topographic marker that influence the trac-

ing of the boundary here. In any case, from its position we can assume Qasr Shemamok was designed to be an observation point on the frontier of the boundary and the Kurdish territories beyond.

As stated before, this strategic location has exposed the site to armed destructions. The American 2002-2003 bombing left, as a result, six large craters still marking the surface of the site (Figures 4 and 5). Evidence of aerial bombing operations in the area, in all likelihood, dates back to late March and early April 2003; i.e. at the time American led Coalition was undertaking *Operation Iraqi Freedom*. The U.S. army's northern operations have been conducted by *the Task Force Viking*¹⁶ whose goal was to contain twelve Iraqi divisions¹⁷ in the North in order to prevent them from intervening in the Bagdad area where Coalition forces were achieving their main thrust¹⁸. The dropping of around 1000 paratroopers of the 173rd Airborne Brigade of the U.S. Army at the civil airport of Bashur led to the seizing of Erbil on March 28th during the *Operation Northern Safari*. Between the 06th and the 10th of April, the Green Berets and Peshmergas marched along the Highway 2 from Erbil to Makhmur facing the 4th Infantry Division of the Iraqi army.

On the 06th of April happened the famous battle of the Dibaga Pass (“Debecka Pass”), situated on the *Green Line*. This battle was broadcasted on media. Located 28.7 km South-East of Qasr Shemamok, it enables the Coalition to penetrate Iraqi lines. During the battle, as was fre-

13. After the Gulf War in 1991 and the establishment of a no-fly zone north of the 36th parallel with the Operations Provide Comfort and Northern Watch, the Iraqi army of Saddam Hussein moved south to this Green Line which consists more like a buffer area of 5 to 40 km wide (ROUSSEL 2014, carte 1; MEIER 2015, p. 96; BOZARSLAN 2009, p. 40). Nevertheless, this line has been established unilaterally by the Iraqi army after 1991 (KANE 2011, p. 20).

14. FONTENOT *et al.* 2004, p. 251.

15. The dimensions of the T54 and T55 tanks are 3.60 m wide and 6.20 m chassis length, which correspond to the rectangular pits, identifies both on Qasr Shemamok and in Dibaga pass aerial imageries. (<https://www.globalsecurity.org/military/world/russia/t-54-specs.htm>).

16. Known as *Joint Special Operations Task Force-North* – FONTENOT *et al.* 2004, p. 90.

17. GILMORE 2004

18. FONTENOT *et al.* 2004, p. 250.

Figure 10: Satellite imagery of the “polemo-shapes” on 1) Qasr Shemamok and 2) Dibaga pass. a) Tank’s entrenchments pits b) Aerial bomb crater c) military trench (QGIS, Bing Map, DigitalGlobe, modified by J.-J. Herr).

quent in US fighting procedures, the Iraqi army positions were first submitted to bombings from F16 and F15 fighter jets. The ridge of the Zurqah Ziraw Dagh and Avanaq hills were hit by Coalition aircraft prior to the engagement of Peshmergas and Green Berets' infantry¹⁹. During the same day, *the Guardian* reports a friendly fire incident near the village of Pir Daoud caused by another airstrike conducted by F15 jets²⁰. According to the Iraqi Kurdistan Democratic Party's newspaper *Brayati*, some days earlier the area was already intensively bombed by the Coalition resulting in the surrender to the Kurdish forces of around 140 Iraqi soldiers on April the 02nd. During this time Saddam Hussein's army withdrew its units from "Awena boundaries" - which probably includes Qasr Shemamok sector – towards the South-West, near the Qara Chawq ("Qarachogh") mountains²¹.

The official record of Coalition activities in the area as well as the public and unclassified documentation concerning these two airstrikes events on the *Green Line* boundaries around Awena suggest that Qasr Shemamok craters could be dated between April the 02nd and 06th 2003. The comparisons of the aerial images of the "polemo-shapes"²² (trenches, tank entrenchments positions and mostly craters) between Qasr Shemamok and the Dibaga pass (Figure 10.1 and Figure 10.2) show remarkably similar features²³. We can therefore safely assume Qasr Shemamok craters are also most probably the result of F15 or F16 fighter jets' bombing.

2.2. Some excavated military installations

While excavating an open area South of Crater 1 (Figure 6) in 2013, the team identified what appeared to be the

Figure 11: Remains of an Iraqi military barrack, 2013 (© MAFQS, photo by M. G. Micale).

19. FONTENOT *et al.* 2004, p. 250-252; LEFAVOR 2013, p. 88-89; GRESHAM 2015. (<https://www.defensemianetwork.com/stories/battle-debecka-pass-roughnecks-war/>)

20. HARDING & HOWARD 2003.

21. UNITED NATIONS HIGH COMMISSIONER FOR REFUGEES 2004, p. 2.

22. Or morphological traces of warfare. TABORELLI *et al.* 2017.

23. 6 km to the East of Qasr Shemamok similar "polemo-shapes" are also visible East of the village of Khazna near the Erbil Steel Factory.

Figure 12: Pit dug by the Saddam's regime soldiers, Locus QSo3BK2I (© MAFQS, photo by M. G. Micale).

remains of the Iraqi military installations targeted during the Coalition's airstrike. The findings consisted in mud-brick walls and a cement floor belonging to a military barrack. Some drains for sewage purposes (Figure 11) were logically placed facing the northern gully to ease out wastewater evacuation. The remains of a defensive trench and a 2x2m square pit were also found in the North-East part of the excavation's trench (QSo3BK2I Figure 12)²⁴.

As a matter of fact, the only "polemo-shapes" visible to the naked eye on the surface of the acropolis are the peripheral trenches and craters displayed in the aerial views of the site.

As shown by ground evidence, the rest of the site appears to have been submitted to systematic levelling activities, carried out by the population living around it. They still continue to do it in order to keep the surface of the tell undisturbed as we have noticed with the removal of our pill of excavated soil South-West of the area B-east (Fig-

ure 6). The photograph clearly shows how the freshly removed ground (more brownish than the dry white and yellowish sediment of the surface) has been spread around modern graves.

The conduction of levelling activities also impacted the morphology of the crater itself. When compared to the other craters, Crater 1's southern limit does not display the distinctive raised rim (or lip/collard) it should have. Specialized studies conducted on the cratering of soil due to explosive ordnance, called "*bombturbation*", have analysed the effects of this violent event on the ground, namely the many disturbances it causes on the soil and its drastic impact on deeper layers. Hupy and Schaetzl have described this phenomenon studying the case of the WWI battlefield of Verdun²⁵. According to their research, an aerial bomb exploding on the surface or underneath the ground surface leaves "a pit that is variously excavated of soil and underlying parent material, with an accom-

24. According to inhabitants these installations have been dug by the warriors of the Iraqi Army in order to hide from the U.S. warplanes sights. Simple roofing with reeds and mud covered the top. The backed brick fragments visible on the photo might have supported a floor, keeping the soldiers out of a muddy surface during spring and winter seasons.

25. HUPY & SCHAETZL 2006.

panying rim of debris nearby”²⁶. This rim is made out of the material excavated by the blast and ejected with equal forces falling to the surface, regularly around the cavity. Our excavation results show that the material coming from the former rim caused by the explosion was later pushed inside “Crater 1” making the stratigraphic entity o3Bo2o in the section (Figure 8).

The crater was also used for littering purposes. Ammunition remains of past fights were discarded into it and are to be found within the backfill. The excavation of the layer yielded various ammunition remains including nose fuses and shells from 82mm and 60mm mortar high explosive rounds (probably of Bulgarian or Yugoslavian origin), and assault rifle AK47 casings and cartridges²⁷ as well as artillery shells debris (Figure 13).

2.3. Archaeology of warfare: a “bomburbation” case study

Since we know that the craters marking the surface of the mound are due to aerial bombing, we can propose in the present section a closer analysis of the disturbances in the stratigraphy of the site. The scope of this section is, therefore, to pick up on different traces of the disturbances phenomenon which affect the soil due to aerial bombing in order to facilitate dealing with such “polemo-shapes” while excavating on a damaged site.

This phenomenon has been identified as a single taphonomic process by geologists within the field of “*impacturbation*” firstly focused on the effect produced by a meteorite on the soil²⁸. In order to differentiate their study case from the meteorite process, Hupy and Schaeztl used the name “*bomburbation*” in the Verdun context²⁹. Despite this differentiation, the case of Qasr Shemamok does show various similarities with the meteorite impact

model and therefore can rightly muster some of its methods and vocabulary in order to provide better criteria of definition of the soil disturbances noticed within the stratigraphy.

The archaeological levels and their successions will not be studied here. Our work will be limited to specific traces of an aerial bomb exploding within the stratigraphy. The marks left by such projectile provide evidence for the three main stages of crater formation, namely *the contact and compression, the excavation* and *the modification* of the sediment³⁰. The purpose of the present study is to identify undisturbed archaeological levels located underneath the *transient cavity*, which results from these three different stages, and to predict the situation an archaeologist may encounter if an excavation of such similar soil disturbance is planned.

2.3.1 Presentation of the craters and their shapes

Nowadays six large craters measuring more than 10 m in diameter mark the surface of the citadel of Qasr Shemamok (Figure 4). Crater 1 is 23 m wide, n° 2 is 18 m, n° 3 is 21 m, n° 4 is 19 m, n° 5 is 12 and n° 6 is 12 m. For comparing purposes, Dibaga sites craters display equivalent shapes and sizes (around 20m wide) (Figure 10.2). The identification with a F15 bombing allows us to assume the Explosive Ordnance hit the ground following a vertical or 45 degrees trajectory.

Each of these craters has a clear halo regularly distributed around the excavated central area (Figures 4, 5 and 10). Today, it is essentially visible for craters 2, 3, 4 and 5. These traces, named the *ejecta*, consist of loose earth and debris located in the immediate vicinity of the crater and form a “lip” around the rim. According to Hupy and Schaeztl, this type of crater is “often formed by conven-

26. HUPY & SCHAEZTL 2006, p. 826.

27. Identification made by D. Leonard, Demining/EOD Consultant (Adem Consulting) and G. Robin (EHM and IM Project Manager | United Nations Mine Action Service). I am very grateful to both of them for their proof reading and comments on this article.

28. OSINSKI & PIERAZZO 2013a.

29. HUPY & SCHAEZTL 2006.

30. OSINSKI & PIERAZZO 2013b, p. 3.

31. HUPY & SCHAEZTL 2006, p. 831.

Figure 13: Ammunitions found inside the Crater r's backfill. 1 Debris of the aerial bomb found underneath the centre of the crater. 2 AK47 cartridges. 3 Fuse nose of 82 mm round mortar. 4 Body of 82 mm round mortar. 5 Zone of deposit of ammunitions recovered in the crater's backfill. (© MAFQS, photos by J.-J. Herr).

Figure 14: Southern part of the Eastern section in Area B showing the listric faults, 2013 (© MAFQS, photo by J.-J. Herr).

tional artillery rounds and aerial munitions” . Such traces are classified by U.S. Army as “Type B crater”³¹.

2.3.2 Excavation in Crater 1: documenting traces of “*bombturbation*”

Identifying this phenomenon helps better understanding the depositional process in this location and therefore the sorting of what belongs to a mixed or disturbed material (*allochthonous* sediment) from preserved levels of occupation (*autochthonous* sediment). Thus, this approach considers the stratigraphy according to a different perspective and not only according to possible identifiable ancient architectural levels. The taphonomy, namely the post-depositional process and the perturbation affecting the stratigraphy are the main focuses of the approach. In “*impacturbation*”, the geologists usually try to identify *impactites*, i.e. “*rocks* produced or affected by hypervelocity impact even”³². In an archaeological site we substitute “*rocks*” by “*sediments*”. According to the *impacturbation*

model, the *impactites* can be subdivided into three categories:

- Autochthonous (“formed on site” , and subsequently dated before the impact event)
- Parautochthonous (“Displaced by the event but sharing a local origin”)
- Allochthonous (“formed elsewhere and clearly moved to their current location” , consequence of the impact, therefore dated after the impact)³³

The excavation of the northern part of “Crater 1” ended after the 2013’s season with the usual stratigraphic profile in which archaeological remains have been identified in the eastern section (Figure 8). The profile highlights in yellow, orange and brown the archaeological remains of walls, floors and ancient deposits. The cut made by the aerial bomb is clearly visible on the left and on the right of the section. Fractures appeared due to the peripheral effect of the explosion and are *listric faults* (Figure 14). The

32. GRIEVE & THERRIAULT 2013, p. 90.

33. Grieve and Therriault 2013, p. 90.

different stratigraphic layers slide along the fault plane. These fractures cut the stratigraphy obliquely on a 60° - 75° angle. Farther east, they ended where remains of mud brick walls have been recovered. These fractures are related to the *excavation stage*, when, due to the explosion, a hemispherical shock wave propagates out into the *autochthonous* sediment³⁴.

Figure 15: Northern part of Area B, 2013. (© MAFQS, photo by J.-J. Herr).

Next to the fractures, we can see the dark colours of the sediment (Figure 15). During the excavation, we understood progressively that these burnt traces were associated with parts of the bomb which penetrated deep beneath the impact spot, as proven by the finding of many

metallic elements related to the debris of the bomb³⁵ (Figure 13.5). This burnt sediment caused by the rapid and explosive release of energy that caused the spreading of a mass of hot combusting gases that form a circular shock wave surrounding the point of impact³⁶. In this part, we can clearly see in the section that the sediment has been removed as well as the mud bricks which appeared to have been disintegrated. This trace of the “shock wave” marks what Hupy and Schaetzl named the result of the “bombturbative force”. It moves the soil from the crater “as it radiates out in a nearly uniform circle”. Beneath the shock wave, the team still found, in a sounding in October 20th 2017, a layer of sediment disintegrated with chunks of soil probably coming from the damaged mud bricks (Figure 18). The bombturbative force can be directly seen on a roughly 50 cm to 1 m thick mantle on the crater’s surface. Such mantle is the *Parautochthonous impactite*. It consists of the original stratigraphic structure composed by disintegrated material, which slid along the fractures and the cuts.

Shock waves cause the sediment to be set in motion³⁷, with an initial outward radial trajectory (which produces the *ejecta*) and a following downward-directed rarefaction which produces an “excavation flow-field and generate a *transient cavity*”³⁸. “The *transient cavity* is partitioned into an upper excavated zone and a lower displaced zone”³⁹. Usually, such impact results in a bowl shape. In Crater 1, however, after having excavated right underneath the central bottom surface, the team found the *Parautochthonous impactite* going up from west to the center of the crater as shown on the southern section of the crater (Figure 16). With meteorites, this phenomenon, named central uplift (SU), is usually distinctive of the “complex crater” and consist of the uplift of the *transient cavity floor* due to an

34. OSINSKI *et al.* 2013, p. 43.

35. The debris could not help to identify the type of aerial bomb, neither the quantity of explosive charge contained in it. Nevertheless, the dimension of the crater’s diameter, bigger than 15 m, might argue for the use of a bomb bigger than 900 kg such as the MK 84. For comparison, see TUCKER 2014, p. 316.

36. HUPY & SCHAETZL 2006, p. 830.

37. OSINSKI *et al.* 2013, p. 43.

38. OSINSKI & PIERAZZO 2013b, p. 4-6.

39. OSINSKI & PIERAZZO 2013b, p. 4.

Figure 16: View from the northern limit of Area B, 2017 (© MAFQS, photo by M. G. Masetti-Rouault).

Figure 17: Western part of the southern section in area B, 2017 (© MAFQS, photo by M. G. Masetti-Rouault).

inward and upward movement of material related to the *modification stage*⁴⁰. At approximately 2 meters beneath the top of the uplift, a fragment of the bomb was recovered (Figure 9). Other *listric faults* are also visible on the southern section more to the East and are parallel to the eastern slope. (Figure 17).

Thanks to these observations and interpretations, we can tentatively propose a hypothetical reconstruction of the entire profile of a crater such as “Crater 1” in Qasr Shemamok made in 2003 by an aerial bomb dropped most probably by a F16 or F15 U.S. fighter jet (Figure 19).

The crater has a 23 meters diameter (at rim level) and

has a *transient cavity floor* located around 6.90 m (dt) from what could have been the original ground surface. Considering a similar density and nature of the sediment at Qasr Shemamok⁴¹, we can deduce from this a hypothetical ratio corresponding to a third of the dimension of the rim diameter (D) is equal to the *transient cavity floor* depth in the center (namely $D/3=dt$). In order to verify the validity of this ratio, it should be compared to other airstrike cases for further studies on such aerial bomb impact. If correct, it could predict at which depth the *autochthonous* sediments, namely, the undisturbed archaeological stratigraphy, should be found at the site of Qasr Shemamok.

3. CONCLUSION

Digging of Crater 1 allowed us not only to get quickly through the more recent stratigraphy and reach the Iron Age and the Late Bronze Age levels, but also gave us an occasion to realize the impact of contemporary armed conflicts on a site which had already been destroyed, remodelled and restructured by prior military events.

Dominating the surrounding plains and conveniently placed on the *Green Line*'s outline, Qasr Shemamok has been a key location for Saddam's infantry divisions overlooking Kurdish territory. This location exposed the site directly to the armed conflicts and in early April 2003 the US-led coalition's F15 and F16 fighter jets targeted the military installation. This results in six large craters with diameter larger than 10, 15 and 20 m.

The excavations of Crater 1 (23 m diameter) by the MAFQS team during two campaigns help to understand the disturbances affecting the stratigraphy caused by aerial bombing.

In order to reach the unaltered layers, named the *autochthonous* sediment, it is necessary to identify the displaced zone, the *paraautochthonous* and the *allochthonous* sediments. The *paraautochthonous* is marked by *listric faults* and chunks of material distributed on a band 50 cm to 1 m thick radiating around the crater. Its end marks the *transient cavity floor* and the beginning of the *autochthonous* sediment. At the bottom of the crater a central uplift is to be expected from which debris of bomb could be found even 2 m deep down in the *autochthonous* sediment.

Later erosion and back filling of the Crater 1 modified its aspect. UXO (Unexploded Ordnance) and ammunitions have been found in the upper layers of the excavated part of the cavity.

Such excavation must be planned with EOD Technicians in order to get quickly and safely to the *autochthonous* sediment, namely the preserved archaeological stratigraphy.⁴²

40. OSINSKI & PIERAZZO 2013b, p. 8.

41. Indeed, we must consider also the nature of the sediments which can affect the resistance to the shock wave released by the explosion.

42. We would like to thank L. Jalabert d'Amado for the proof reading of this article.

Figure 18: Northern part of area B. Sounding underneath the centre and the western part of the Crater 1, 2017 (© MAFQS, photo by M. G. Masetti-Rouault).

Figure 19: Sketch of the Crater 1 section. D Final Crater diameter (rim-to-rim). d Apparent depth. dSU Original ground surface-to-central uplift depth. dt True depth, SU Central Uplift (realised by J.-J. Herr).

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